

THE PLACE AND ROLE OF PIANO PERFORMANCE ART IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEK ENTERTAINING ART

Rakhimova Mavludakhan Nabijanovna

Andijan State University

Teacher of the Department of Music Education of the Faculty of Arts

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10254327>

Abstract: This article discusses the development of Estrada art in Uzbek music culture. Opinions were also given about the importance of piano performance in the development of folk art in our country.

Key words: Variety, genre, piano, musical culture, barometer, stage.

Musical variety is a means of actively developing emotional feelings that quickly affect a person. It is known that by getting to know music, you can enjoy music for a lifetime. In general, music is an integral part of the human psyche. Music is an art form that occupies a large place in our cultural life and plays an important role in the development of human personality. As we know, piano music performance, which is considered important in the history of world music, is based on the solo performance style according to its essence, but it also requires ensemble performance. Therefore, piano lessons occupy an important place in the educational programs and plans of musical educational institutions for teaching the piano specialty.¹ It is not without reason that in the piano class of children's music and art schools, the student not only completes the initial stage of musical literacy, but also acquires the skill of playing in cooperation for the first time.

It is known from musicology that there are various currents and genres in music, of which the most popular today is Estrada genre. The pop genre in music teaches to correctly perceive and appreciate the beautiful things around. Music equips a person with high taste, shapes his spiritual outlook. This system has the ability to strongly influence human feelings and is an important means of introducing students to the world of sophistication and moral education.

We can see the musical works of the pop genre in the performer of vocals and musical instruments. Estrada's works, especially as a vocal singer and piano player, have been described by musicologists for their unusual melodies and harmonic sounds.

First of all, if we analyze the meaning and origin of Estrada, Estrada is derived from Spanish and means board. In a broad sense, it is a general expression of entertainment, popular artistic (eternal, musical, dance, entertainment, etc.) genres and forms. Also, in a narrow sense, it is considered a type of professional stage art. In Russia and other countries, it is called Estrada, music hall in England, variety, cafechantan, cabaret in France, show, revue in the USA.²

¹ Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 713-718.

² Russkaya sovetskaya estrada // Essays on history. Otv. ed. Ph.D. isk., prof. E.Uvarova. V 3-x T. M., 2012.

Although pop art has its origins in folklore, it emerged as a specific (commercial) art form in the 19th century in the democratic socio-cultural environment of large European cities. The main form of Estrada is Estrada concerts held regularly in special places. It consists of small performances of several (or single) artists (lyricists, singers, dancers, actors, etc.) with artistic completeness and diverse content, and is distinguished by the expressiveness and brightness of the means of expression, originality, and the direct communication of the participants with the audience. In Europe, variety shows were first held in cafes and restaurants, later in adapted theater buildings and other venues. They featured wordsmiths, singers, dancers and dancers, as well as acrobats and blindfolders.

It is known that each era or time has its own spiritual world based on its level of development. The demand specific to the needs of the society is formed in proportion to the time of the worldviews suitable to the taste. The new way of thinking, attitudes and worldviews formed due to our independence are the basis of our unique idea of national independence. This is a sign of the spiritual perfection of the future great country. Today's main demands are to be independent in every field, to restore our national values and to operate within the framework of world standards. We can see this in the rapid development of modern composers' work and in the spread of pop music forms among our people. In our music, universal musical forms, imbued with the spirit of the times, are developing more and more. It should be noted that the original state of our modern music is being enriched with new secular genres, typical of our day. Folk music can be said to be the manifestation of our national traditions and rituals in the tones. These examples are closely related to the daily life, training and national values of our people. In order to preserve them and pass them on to the next generation, special folklore ensembles have been established and are currently operating.

The word Estrada means "hill" in Latin. In the 50s of the 20th century, the word pop entered music and began to be used as a small form of performing arts. Pop music is a leading part of pop art. Estrada is popular music of a light household character, the history of its formation begins with the theater and performance forms of Western nations. It developed from the interaction of the coffeehouse and music hall cultures popularized in the West. Asta - slow jazz, European and Eastern harmony and rhythm, rock, pop, etc. In Uzbekistan, pop music began to form in the 50s of the 20th century. It was founded by the well-known pop star Botir Zakirov. In 1957, the young pop group from Uzbekistan successfully participated for the first time in the VI International Festival of Youth held in Moscow and won the proud 4th place. It was a great achievement. After that, pop music quickly became popular and developed. Pop groups such as "Yalla", "Pakhtaoy", "Navo", "Sado" were formed.

Estrada music occupies a special place in the work of modern composers. A number of Uzbek composers have created and continue to work in this direction. For example, Rustam Abdullayev, Khabibullo Rahimov, Nadim Narkhodjayev, Dilorom Amannulayeva, Avaz Mansurov, Khurshida Hasanova, Aydin Abdullayeva and many other young composers are working effectively. Working in the pop song genre requires a lot from the composer: to have a sensitive sense of time, to be a kind of "barometer", to take into account the artistic taste of the audience, to choose appropriate topics. Describing pop songs of Uzbek composers, it should be noted that they correspond to the general development of our time. "The stylistic direction in pop art," says D. Amanullayeva, "is a unique "fashion" determined by the era and the listener. The song is a reflection of time, a "mirror" of our life.

Composer D. Amanullayev has published a number of academic manuals for the development of pop songs³: *"Pop songs" (Tashkent., 2007)*, pop-jazz vocalists (Tashkent., 2014), pop songs (Tashkent., 2015), which are included in the educational process and are fundamental educational material for pop students is considered. In this genre, only composers who are in tune with the times will be able to achieve their good results. The uniqueness of the pop genre, which has brought many composers of Uzbekistan wide popularity among the mass audience, has opened a new, interesting, active creative path for many composers.

In the 1970s and 1980s, almost all composers of that time, Mutal Burkhanov, Manas Leviyev, Sharif Ramazanov, Gafur Kadirov, I. Akbarov, I. Hamrayev, worked in the genre of pop music, and this is connected with the search for unique national means of expression. was liq. Composer Ikram Akbarov wrote *"Ra'no"*, *"Gazli kokhliklari"*, *"Makhbubga"*, *"Ketma Nigor"*, *"Kaydasan"*, *"Yor kel"* specially written and performed for the first time by famous pop singer Botir Zakirov, People's Artist of Uzbekistan. , pop songs such as *"Koshchinor"*, *"Kor yoghar"*, *"Bakhor Vasli"*, *"Azizim"*, *"Lolazor chorlaydi"* gained fame with their charm in the work of Uzbek pop composers. This rise in pop art gave the world bright examples, which later became classics of Uzbek pop art. Also, as we know, children's songs occupy a special place in pop music, they require the composer to know children's psychology, children's vocal data and voice abilities, the ability to sensitively feel the children's world, its variety and diversity. One of the signs of updating the musical system of the composer's children's song is the departure from the previous experiences of the composers (D. Saydaminova, A. Mansurov, D. Amanullayev) and the technique of pop music expected by the activities of the first children's VIA (Pakhtaoy, Guncha) created in the 1980s. allows for wide use.

*The pop song by the Uzbek composer focuses on people, their feelings and thoughts. In this genre, various topics and plots aimed at reflecting modern human life and its time are covered*⁴. Composers find their own rhythm intonations, means of musical expression, placement of musical materials for their songs, but the most important thing in songs is the melody that composers create from the best musical language - chanting, characteristic of Uzbek song lyrics, and thus continuing the tradition. Today, Uzbek pop music corresponds to the basics of musical art trends and meets all the requirements and indicators of this genre.

Currently, tasks such as the development of Estrada art, coordination of the activities of Estrada groups and individual performers are assigned to the "Uzbeknavo" association. Estrada is included in the special education system as a field of study. Since 1996, Variety faculties have been operating in Tashkent Pop College, Uzbekistan State Conservatory and other art (music) educational institutions.

Also, in 2021, based on the decision of the president, the "National Pop Art Institute named after Botir Zakirov under the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan" was established.⁵ Of course, this also has a positive effect on the further development of Estrada art.

Summary.

³ Амануллаева Д. Обзор стилистических направлений вокально-джазового искусства Узбекистана (1991 – 2009 гг.) // Процессы реформирования системы музыкального образования. Т., 2009.

⁴ История узбекской советской музыка, том III. Т., 1991.

⁵ O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining qarori, 16.10.2021 yildagi PQ-5261-son

From the above, it should be concluded that the development of Estrada art in our country has had a positive and negative impact on Uzbek music culture. Piano performance is important in the development of pop art, because Pop music was originally written for vocals and piano, and therefore has its place.

References:

- 1 Russkaya sovetskaya estrada // Essays on history. Otv. ed. Ph.D. isk., prof. E.Uvarova. V 3-x T. M., 2012.
2. Vermenich Yu. va bu jazz. Sankt-Peterburg: Nevskiy jamg'armasi, 2005. 448 p.
- 3.Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. Science and Education, 3(3), 713-718.
- 4.Амануллаева Д. Обзор стилистических направлений вокально-джазового искусства Узбекистана (1991 – 2009 гг.) // Процессы реформирования системы музыкального образования. Т., 2009.